

Synthesis and characterization of nickel(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II), copper(II), iron(III) and chromium(III) complexes of unsymmetrical salen-type ligand and their application as catalysts for the oxidation of styrene

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Manuscript received 29 December 2008, revised 23 March 2009, accepted 24 March 2009

Abstract : Salen type ligand has been synthesized in high yield, from which the nickel(II), cobalt(II), manganese(II), copper(II), iron(III) and chromium(III) complexes have been synthesized. The resulting complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, IR and electronic spectral data, magnetic susceptibility measurements and thermogravimetric analysis. The complexes have been tested for their ability to activate molecular oxygen in the catalytic oxidation of styrene. Manganese(II), nickel(II) and chromium(III) complexes show slight high catalytic activity towards oxidation of styrene as compared to others. Scanning electron micrograph and powder X-ray diffractogram have also been reported.

Keywords : Imines, tetradentate Schiff base ligand, thermogravimetry, catalytic oxidation of styrene.

Introduction

Recent interest in the synthesis and characterization of unsymmetrical tetradentate Schiff base complexes has been prompted by the belief that systematic investigation of these complexes may throw light on the nature of complexes of biological interest. In these complexes, the metal ion is in an unsymmetrical ligand environment. Schiff base ligands are able to co-ordinate metal through imine nitrogen and another group, usually linked to the aldehyde. Usually, tetradentate, salen-type chelating ligands are symmetrical and are therefore, readily synthesized, whereas the preparation of unsymmetrical ligand is by no mean trivial^{1,2}. However the latter offer remarkable structural variation of the complexes derived from these, which may provide useful catalyst for the activation of molecular oxygen. Salen type ligand with N and O atoms are important since their metal complexes find widespread applications as homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts for the epoxidation of styrene³⁻⁶. Metal complexes prepared from such ligand have become the focus of attention of highly active catalyst for olefin polymerization. Our present efforts are aimed at developing such unsymmetrical salen-type Schiff base derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone and ethylene diamine by literature method⁷ and its complexes with Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} and characterized and tested towards catalytic oxidation of styrene.

Results and discussion

All the metal complexes are coloured solids, air stable, non-hygroscopic and insoluble in water and common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in hot DMF and DMSO. The elemental analysis shows 1 : 1 metal to ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes. The analytical data of the complexes is given in Table 1.

Electronic absorption spectra : The electronic absorption spectrum of ligand shows a broad band at 322 nm due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition associated with the azomethine group and another band around 264 nm which may arise from a transition involving mainly the π molecular orbital localized on the C=N group and/or the aromatic ring⁸⁻¹¹.

The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex shows absorption bands at 769, 600 and 425 nm corresponding to square planar geometry. These bands may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively¹². Cobalt complex display absorption bands at 730, 590 and 360 nm corresponding to $^4T_{1g} \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$, $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$, transitions, respectively for an octahedral geometry¹³. Mn^{II} complex exhibits bands at 570, 430 and 350 nm corresponding to $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(^4G)$, $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_{2g}$, $^4A_{1g}(^4G)$ and $^6A_{1g} \rightarrow ^4E_{2g}(^4D)$, transitions, respectively suggesting octahedral environment around Mn^{II} ion¹⁴. Cu^{II} complex display bands

Table 1. Analytical and spectral data of ligand and its complexes

Compd.	Colour	M.p./Decom. temp. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :			Infrared frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
			Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$
			C	N	H		
[H ₂ L]	Yellow	110	72.32 (72.39)	9.92 (9.45)	6.42 (6.88)	1634	1283
[NiL]	Golden brown	> 300	60.22 (57.68)	8.27 (8.06)	4.76 (3.29)	1621	1318
[CoL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Mohawk valley	> 300	54.41 (56.48)	7.47 (8.82)	5.37 (4.42)	1598	1303
[MnL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Copper leaf	> 300	50.13 (45.12)	5.94 (5.34)	6.88 (6.19)	1624	1300
[CuL(H ₂ O) ₂]	Gold standard	> 300	49.08 (41.67)	6.74 (6.09)	5.82 (3.63)	1626	1297
[FeLCl(H ₂ O)]	Brown	> 300	47.97 (43.34)	6.58 (5.27)	5.20 (3.80)	1628	1305
[CrLCl(H ₂ O)]	Leaf brown	> 300	46.41 (50.84)	6.37 (5.20)	5.50 (5.37)	1626	1292

at 800, 600 and 438 nm due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and charge transfer transitions, respectively, suggesting distorted octahedral geometry¹⁵. Fe^{III} complex shows bands at 800, 460 and 370 nm assignable to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(G)$, transitions, respectively, expected for an octahedral structure⁷. Cr^{III} complex exhibits bands at 600, 440 and 350 nm which may be attributed to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, transitions, respectively, indicating an octahedral geometry around Cr^{III} ion¹⁶.

Infrared spectra :

The characteristic vibrational frequencies have been identified by comparing the spectra of the complexes with that of the parent ligand and literature value of absorption of simple type of compound. The Schiff base exhibits a medium broad band at 3052 cm⁻¹, which may be due to the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between phenolic hydrogen and azomethine nitrogen atom^{17,18}. The absence of this band in the spectra of complexes indicate the deprotonation of the phenolic group and coordination of the oxygen atom to the metal ion. This is further supported by the shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) band from 1283 cm⁻¹¹⁹ of ligand to 1293–1339 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of complexes, indicating the coordination of phenolic oxygen atom to the metal ion²⁰. The strong band observed at 1635 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch in the ligand spectrum has been shifted to lower frequency by ca. 10–40 cm⁻¹ upon coordination^{21–24}. The bonding

through oxygen and nitrogen is further supported by the appearance of new bands in the region 510–550 and 400–440 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibrations respectively²⁵. On the basis of these results, it can be concluded that in the complexes, the Schiff base behave as tetradentate ligand.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra :

The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra of the free ligand were recorded in CDCl₃. The free ligand exhibits peak at 13.3 and 16.0 ppm respectively due to hydrogen-bonded phenolic -OH protons. The multiplets observed at 6.85–7.53 ppm are assigned to the aromatic protons. The coordination of diamine with the carbonyl carbon in synthesized unsymmetrical ligand is supported by the appearance of two singlet for alkyl protons =N-CH₂-CH₂-N= at δ 3.9284 and 3.9667 ppm respectively^{8,25}.

The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the free ligand exhibits signals for carbon (C8) and (C9) of =N-CH₂-CH₂-N= at 50.07 and 59.64 ppm²⁵. The signals observed at 166.41 and 172.65 ppm²⁵ are assigned for carbon (C7) and (C10) from imine group -N=C<.

Magnetic properties :

The magnetic moment determination shows that the Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic, which suggests square planar geometry of complex⁷. The Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes exhibit magnetic moments of 5.68, 5.65, 3.96 and 3.17 B.M. respectively, indicating their high spin

nature and octahedral environment around the metal ion^{13-16,26}. In case of Cu^{II} complex magnetic moment was found to be 2.09 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired electron, suggesting distorted octahedral geometry around the copper²⁷. The higher observed magnetic moment values may be due to orbital contributions.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

All the complexes show almost similar thermal decomposition pattern and weight loss continues till a stable metal oxide is formed. The TG and DTA curves reveal that ligand (H₂L) decomposes in 2 steps. The first exothermic peak at about 293 °C and second endothermic peak at 580 °C. The Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes losses their two coordinated water molecules in the 140–180 °C temperature, while Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes show loss of one coordinated water molecule in this temperature region. The anhydrous complexes remain stable up to ~280 °C and there after the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecule as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continuous up to ~700 °C and on further increasing the temperature no weight loss is observed which may be attributed to the formation of stable metal oxide²⁸. The thermal decomposition of Ni^{II} complex takes place in the temperature range of 320–620 °C and for this decomposition, the DTA curve shows exothermic peak at 300 °C. In the second stage of pyrolysis, another peak at 475 °C in the DTA curve indicates that this degradation stage is endothermic in nature. The Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes decomposes in three steps and leaving behind residue as metal oxides. Horowitz-Metzger method²⁹ has been used for the finding kinetic parameters of the complexes. The thermoanalytical data of all the complexes is given in Table 2. The negative values of entropy change indicates that the activated complex has a

more ordered structure than the reactants and the reactions are slower than normal. Further the low values of Z suggest that the decomposition reaction of complexes can be classified as a slow nature of the reaction.

Scanning electron micrograph study :

The scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of metal complexes indicate the presence of well defined crystals free from any shadow of the metal ion on their external surface. The representative micrographs of (a) [NiL], (b) [CoL(H₂O)₂], (c) [MnL(H₂O)₂], (d) [CuL(H₂O)₂], (e) [FeLCl(H₂O)] and (f) [CrLCl(H₂O)] are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of complexes.

Catalytic activity of complexes :

The oxidation of styrene, catalyzed by Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes was carried out using H₂O₂ as an oxidant and gave styrene oxide as major product with minor amounts of phenyl acetaldehyde as side product. Epoxidation of styrene resulted in the 0.20–8.062% conversion and 48.5–69.91% selectivity of styrene into styrene oxide (Fig. 2). No significant side products were identified.

X-Ray diffractogram :

The powder X-ray diffraction pattern was recorded for Ni^{II} complex in the range 2θ = 10.96–58.05°. The X-ray powder diffractogram of Ni^{II} complex exhibits sharp peaks indicating the crystalline nature of the complex (Fig. 3).

Table 2. Thermal decomposition data of complexes

Complex	Half decomposition temp. (°C)	Activation energy E _a (KJ mol ⁻¹)	Frequency factor Z (s ⁻¹)	Entropy change (-ΔS) (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
[NiL]	590	28.66	15.98	228.55
[CoL(H ₂ O) ₂]	565	43.47	22.01	227.84
[MnL(H ₂ O) ₂]	423	25.30	28.97	207.262
[CuL(H ₂ O) ₂]	501	28.89	34.83	223.363
[FeLCl(H ₂ O)]	520	25.79	25.45	226.174
[CrLCl(H ₂ O)]	567	40.26	36.93	223.55

Fig. 2. Catalytic reactivity of complexes : (□) % selectivity, (■) % conversion.

Material and methods :

All the chemical and solvents used were of analytical grade. Salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone, ethylenediamine were obtained from Merck Chemicals. *N*-

(Salicylidene)-*N'*-(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-ethylenediamine was prepared by reported procedure⁷.

Synthesis of *N*-(salicylidene)-*N'*-(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-ethylenediamine (*H₂L*) :

An ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde (2.44 g, 20 mmol) was added to a solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (2.723 g, 20 mmol) and the mixture was kept in an ice bath for 30 min. To this an ethanolic solution of ethylene diamine (1.2 g, 20 mmol) was added dropwise while stirring magnetically. The yellow colored compound formed (Scheme 1) was suction filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol and then dried *in vacuo*. Thin layer chromatography studies indicate the presence of only one compound. Yield 90.80%, m.p. 110 °C (Found : C, 72.30; H, 6.88; N, 9.35. Calcd. : C, 72.32; H, 6.42; N, 9.92); UV-Vis : 322.4 (*n* → π^*), 264.8 nm (π → π^*); IR (KBr) : 3052 (phenolic -OH), 1634 (C=N), 1283 cm^{-1} (C-O); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 2.4 (3H, s), 3.9284 (2H, s, CH₂-N=), 3.9667 (2H, s, CH₂-N=), 6.85–7.53 (8H, m, aryl-H), 13.3 (1H, s, phenolic -OH) and 16.0 (1H, s, phenolic -OH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 14.65, 50.07, 59.64, 116.87, 117.30, 118.41, 118.59, 119.38, 128.10, 131.41,

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffractogram of Ni^{II} complex.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of *N*-(salicylidene)-*N'*-(*o*-hydroxyacetophenone)-ethylenediamine (H_2L).

132.30, 132.39, 160.94, 163.94, 166.41, 172.65 ppm.

Preparation of metal complexes :

The metal salts used for the preparation of complexes were $NiCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, anhydrous $FeCl_3$, $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$. Equimolar proportions of metal chloride and ligand (2 mmol) were dissolved separately in minimum quantity (25 mL) of DMF. Both the solutions were filtered and then mixed in hot with constant stirring. The mixture was then refluxed at 135 °C for an hour on a sand bath. Then pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.5 using alcoholic ammonia and further refluxed for 3 h. It was allowed to cool to room temperature and coloured products obtained were filtered, washed with DMF and hot ethanol and dried over calcium chloride in a desiccator.

Physical measurements :

The analysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed on Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer at Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow, India. The infrared spectra of ligand and its complexes were obtained in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer 597 at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra of ligand were taken in $CDCl_3$ using TMS as internal standard on Bruker Auance-II 400 NMR spectrometer at SAIF, Punjab University, Chandigarh. The room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements of the resulting complexes were measured by Gouy's method using $Hg[Co(SCN)_4]$ as calibrant. The diamagnetic contribution of the ligand and the metal ions were computed using Pascal's constants. Thermogravimetric analyses of the complexes were carried out using a Netzsch STA409 thermal analyzer at

RSIC, IIT Madras, Chennai in the temperature range 40–700 °C with a heating rate 20 °C/min. Diffuse reflectance spectra of complexes were recorded on Varian Cary 5E UV-NIR spectrophotometer at RSIC, IIT Madras, Chennai. SEM images of complexes were recorded at VNIT, Nagpur. The XRD measurement of complexes was recorded over a Philips X-ray diffraction analyzer at VNIT, Nagpur, India.

Procedure for catalytic oxidation :

Catalytic oxidation of styrene to corresponding epoxide by $[NiL]$, $[CoL(H_2O)_2]$, $[MnL(H_2O)_2]$, $[CuL(H_2O)_2]$, $[FeLCl(H_2O)]$ and $[CrLCl(H_2O)]$ complexes were studied in presence of an aqueous solution of 30% H_2O_2 as an oxidant (Scheme 2). All catalytic reactions were carried out in 50 ml reaction flask fitted with water condenser. A general procedure was followed for all reactions. In a typical experiment, styrene and 30% H_2O_2 were mixed in 1 : 1 proportion in 5 ml of acetonitrile and

Scheme 2. Epoxidation of styrene into styrene oxide.

the reaction mixture was heated at 60 °C with continuous stirring. An appropriate catalyst to be tested (0.3 g, 0.03 mol) was added to the reaction mixture and heated at 60 °C under constant stirring for 4 h. After the completion of the reaction, an organic layer was separated by separating funnel and analyzed using 19091Z.413 E Agilent Gas Chromatography with HP-1 column having length 30 m and inner diameter 0.32 mm and FID detector.

References

1. P. A. Ganeshpure, W. Adam and C. R. Saha-Moeller, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, 43, 56.
2. M. R. Bermejo, A. M. Gonzalez, M. Fondo, A. Garcid-Deibe, M. Maneiro, J. Sanmartin, O. L. Hoyos and M. Watkinson, *New J. Chem.*, 2000, 24, 235.
3. "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", ed. G. Wilkinson, Pergamon Press, New York, 1987, 2, 6.
4. J. Li, B. Xu, W. Jiang, B. Zhou, W. Zeng and S. Qin, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, 33, 975.
5. M. R. Maurya, A. K. Chandrakar and S. Chand, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2007, 263, 233.
6. M. R. Maurya, U. Kumar, I. Correia, P. Adao and J. C. Pessoa, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, 577.
7. D. Kumar, A. Syamal, Jaipal and P. K. Gupta, *Oriental J.*

- Chem.*, 2005, **21**, 89.
8. J. C. Pessoa and T. Kiss, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, 732.
 9. M. R. Maurya and N. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 542.
 10. R. V. Singh, A. Chaudhari and S. C. Joshi, *Main Group Metal Chem.*, 2004, **27**, 59.
 11. M. Gullotti, A. Pasini, P. Fantucci, R. Ugo and R. D. Gillard, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1972, **102**, 852.
 12. R. M. Holm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5632.
 13. M. B. H. Howlader, M. B. Hossain and N. Akhter, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2008, **47**, 218.
 14. S. Chandra, S. Verma and P. Meera, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 898.
 15. M. N. Patel, J. R. Patel and D. H. Sutaria, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 797.
 16. R. K. Dubey, U. K. Dubey and C. M. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2008, **47**, 1210.
 17. A. R. Sarkar and S. Mandal, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 1477.
 18. P. P. Hankare, R. K. Patil, S. S. Chavan, A. H. Jagtap and P. S. Batlase, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1326.
 19. K. C. Gupta and A. K. Sutar, *J. Mol. Catal. (A) : Chem.*, 2007, **272**, 64.
 20. M. R. Maurya, S. Khurana and D. Rehder, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, 773.
 21. E. P. Aranha, M. P. dos Santos, S. Romera and E. R. Dockal, *Polyhedron*, 2007, **26**, 1373.
 22. R. Vafazadeh and M. Kashfi, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **2817**, 1228.
 23. O. Signorini, E. R. Dockal, G. Castellano and G. Oliva, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **5**, 245.
 24. J. R. Zamian and E. R. Dockal, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1996, **21**, 370.
 25. A. A. Khandar, K. Netaji and Z. Rezvani, *Molecule*, 2005, **10**, 302.
 26. P. R. Reddy and A. M. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2084.
 27. I. H. Bukhari, M. Arif, J. Akbar and A. H. Khan, *Pak. J. Biol. Sci.*, 2005, **8**, 615.
 28. R. K. Verma, L. Verma and M. Chandra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2003, **42**, 2982.
 29. H. H. Horowitz and Metzger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464.